

A spatially explicit framework for future climate change risk assessments

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Summary

Climate emergencies have been declared across the UK and the world, both by local and national governments and by businesses, demonstrating the growing urgency to address the causes and impacts of climate change on societies and economies. Assessing the strategies and measures which can be employed to reduce the impacts of climate change is thus essential. This research aims to provide an open framework enabling the spatially-explicit analysis required to provide consistent assessments of climate impacts and potential adaptation options across scenarios, sectors and measures. An example is provided within a UK context to demonstrate current progress.

KEYWORDS: climate change, spatial modelling framework, risk assessments, climate emergency

1 Background

Over recent years the seriousness and scale at which climate change is impacting Earth and the inhabiting societies, ecosystems, environmental processes and landscapes has been realised with increasing levels of awareness and alarm (IPCC, 2018). Events, such as the ‘heat dome’ in USA in 2021 (National Geographic, 2021), extreme flooding events at scales previously un-seen around the world, such as in Germany (Emergency and Management Service, 2021) can all be, to some extent, attributed to the effects of climate change (Kreienkamp *et al.*, 2021). Many of the effects of climate change are ‘locked-in’, the Earth’s systems being affected to such an extent and functioning on such long-term timescales, that even efforts to achieve net-zero will not protect us from the impacts of climate change for centuries, and as such we need to plan long-term to better protect against the impacts (Hanlon *et al.*, 2021).

In the UK context, the effects of climate change are evident, from the UK’s 10 hottest recorded years all being since 2002 (Met Office, 2019), and recent events such as torrential rain are predicated to occur more regularly and with greater intensity (Met Office, 2021). The response, at governmental and policy level, requires an independent assessment of climate risk in the UK (CCRA) every 5 years, for which the UK and devolved nations must set out responses to climate-related risks through the National Adaptation Programmes; programmes focused on adapting to reduce the impacts of climate change. Such assessments are complex (Figure 1); risk is multi-factored, coupled socioeconomic and natural process and portfolios of policies must be considered in response. Climate change risk is evolving and variable, with the need to consider scenarios of the future, both in terms of the natural and the socioeconomic aspects of risk. Inherent in all of these considerations is a spatial component; climate change effects (hazards), governance and socioeconomic changes are spatial, varying across spatial domains and scales.

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Figure 1: Understanding the components of climate change risk and impacts, and the factors needing to be considered (IPCC, 2012)

2 Framework

This research presents the development of a framework, Figure 2, capable of delivering the tools and models that will underpin the next CCRA exercise for the UK. The framework, developed as part of the OpenCLIM project, couples the latest data on scenarios and drivers for both climate and socioeconomic futures across the UK, with open models and supporting tools enabling an up-to-date, data-driven, and policy-relevant risk assessment across multiple risk sectors. Each risk sector, from the effects of climate change on agriculture, to future flood risks in urban areas, or the effects of increased temperatures on human health, is represented by a ‘workflow’. Built into this modelling is adaptation, and the ability to test and examine the different options within individual models and sectors, as well as across sectors. A series of initial workflows will be developed per risk sector, for example flooding (Figure 3) allowing for an assessment to be undertaken for each. Workflows will, where opportunities arise, be flexible and dynamic, allowing coupling and feedbacks between models and sectors.

The discussed framework will be built on the DAFNI (Data Analytics Facility for National Infrastructure) platform (DAFNI, 2022), a stable production-level environment for data and modelling. The facility will host all models, input data, and output data, and provide an open platform where the framework and its outputs can be accessed. DAFNI is agnostic to data and models, and thus a suite of spatial tools will be developed to enable the coupling of spatially explicit models and the coupling of these independently, previously developed models. The framework will utilise the existing base ‘workflow’ engine, allowing the development of the complex workflows required to model and understand the risks across the identified risk sectors.

The developed open framework has multiple advantages:

- Tools support the use of the same key drivers across all risk sectors, with socioeconomic (e.g. UK SSPs) and climate data (e.g. UKCP18) used as common drivers in the implementation, previously a measure not used in previous CCRA.
- The open nature of the framework and DANFI platform allows users to add their own models, which can either be added to or replace existing models, or be used for new analysis workflows for further risk sectors.
- Results can be interrogated and explored to gain additional value from the modelling and the reasoning behind results.

Figure 2: OpenCLIM framework for climate change impact assessment.

Figure 3: Initial proposed workflow for flooding risk (inland flooding only).

3 Results

Initial work developing the framework has been undertaken developing a number of risk assessment workflows along side the set of spatial tools to spatially enable the DANFI platform and workflow engine. Here we will highlight the flood risk workflow which has been piloted for the Clyde region, and in-particular, central Glasgow.

Using the CityCat Hydrodynamic model (Glenis *et al.*, 2018) a workflow has been established which for any area within Great Britain can run a simulation to assess the levels of surface flooding (e.g Figure 4) under climate scenarios. National scale datasets including a DEM (Digital Elevation Model), a building set, and future climate projections, are employed with the workflow translating these to the area of interest using developed spatial tools, and runs the model for a given parameter set. This allows the workflow to run for any area nationally. Impact assessment models can then be coupled within the workflow to assess potential impacts, such as estimated damages from flooding.

Figure 4: Example of an output from the CityCat Hydrodynamic model of surface water flows and flooding in Glasgow City Centre.

Through the developed framework, further models can easily be coupled. The UDM (Urban Development Model) (Ford *et al.*, 2019) generates plausible development patterns given population projections and land use constraints (Figure 5). This enables not just future climate scenarios to be modelled using the current built environment, but for future land-use to be considered when undertaking such risk-assessments (e.g. Figure 6), allowing decision makers to consider policies around land-use and urban development in consideration to hazard exposure, such as flooding in this case.

Figure 5: Example development scenario for northern Glasgow from the UDM model.

Figure 6: Preliminary results of estimated flood damages within Glasgow City Centre for five socioeconomic scenarios (SSP) for a 100yr flood event at two time periods, 2050 and 2070.

4 Conclusion

This paper has presented the concept and initial work for the design of an open framework for climate change risk assessments, and in particular, the UK's next Climate Change Adaptation Report (CCRA). The presented framework enables a consistent and open methodology allowing for climate change risk assessments to be undertaken, with an initial example presented for Glasgow, UK, highlighting the utility and flexibility of the framework.

Further work will continue to develop the spatial tool set on the DAFNI platform, while workflows are developed for more risk sectors, such as for biodiversity and health from extreme heat. Further consideration to the potential of feedback loops will be given allowing adaptation in sectors to be reflected in the risk assessments of other sectors, while work will be undertaken to understand how to best share and disseminate the results.

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Biographies

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